

Feature-based analyses of concept drift

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Feature selection
Concept drift
Explaining streaming data
Explainable AI

ABSTRACT

Feature selection is one of the most relevant preprocessing and analysis techniques in machine learning. It can dramatically increase the performance of learning algorithms and at the same time provide relevant information on the data. In the scenario of online and stream learning, concept drift, i.e., changes in the underlying distribution over time, can cause significant problems for learning models and data analysis. While there do exist feature selection methods for online learning, none of the methods targets feature selection for drift detection, i.e., the challenge to increase the performance of drift detectors by analyzing the drift rather than increasing model accuracy. However, this challenge is particularly relevant for common unsupervised scenarios. In this work, we study feature selection for drift detection and drift monitoring. We develop a formal definition for a feature-wise notion of drift that allows semantic interpretation. Besides, we derive an efficient algorithm by reducing the problem to classical feature selection and analyze the applicability of our approach to feature selection for drift detection on a theoretical level. Finally, we empirically show the relevance of our considerations on several benchmarks.

1. Introduction

Data collected in real-world applications ranging from social media entries to sensor measurements are subject to continuous changes commonly referred to as concept drift or drift for shorthand [1,2]. There are many different causes for drift. For example, user behavior might change due to seasons or trends and sensor measurements might be affected by environmental effects, and degrading or failing of sensor. Since drift might induce severe problems in machine learning models and render performed data analysis useless, it is important to detect and understand the nature and the characteristics of ongoing drift [3–5].

Feature selection and feature relevance analysis constitute particularly relevant techniques for data preprocessing and analysis in machine learning as well as data science [6–8]. Employing these techniques can dramatically increase generalization capabilities while reducing training time and the amount of training data needed. These factors are of particular relevance in online and stream learning where only limited resources, i.e., limited data and computation time are available [2]. Further, such techniques also provide relevant information about the scenario and enable insights into the global problem structure.

There exist approaches to explaining concept drift [3,5,9] and feature selection for stream learning in the presence of drift [10,11], but only a few approaches consider both problems at once [9]. Feature selection for drift detection, i.e., feature selection to enable better

drift detection performance, is a novel and relevant problem. It is challenging since drift detection does not admit a loss function, hence, well-known feature selection methods do not apply directly. Yet, it is of great interest as it can not only increase performance but also allow relevant insight into the ongoing drift.

In this work, we study feature selection for concept drift detection using a filter-method-like approach. For this purpose, we propose a mathematical formalization of *drifting features*, which fulfills desirable mathematical properties which we derive from the quantitative measure of *drift intensity*. We link this mathematical formalization to feature selection tasks in the context of a regression problem, utilizing an alternative characterization of drift as the dependency of observation and time [12].

This paper is an extended version of [13]. The original paper only explores the theory for a single, specific drift intensity. It does not cover the connection of drift intensity and drift detectors thoroughly. Also, it only provides limited empirical evidence. On a theoretical level, we study drift intensities and analyze the relevance for different drift detection schemes, i.e., windowing schemes, distance measures, etc., connecting them to the resulting notion of drifting features. On an empirical level, we extend the experiments on the advances in the performance of drift detection algorithms.

This paper is organized as follows (see also Fig. 1): first, we recall the definition of concept drift (Section 2.2) and then propose the notion

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2024.127968>

Received 17 February 2024; Received in revised form 10 May 2024; Accepted 29 May 2024

Available online 22 June 2024

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Fig. 1. Visual summary of results and structure of this paper. We introduce *drifting features* with a focus on *monitoring/model-based explanations* based on the concept of *drift intensity* which we develop in Section 3. We then derive an *efficient algorithmic solution* for finding drifting features based on common *feature selection techniques* in Section 4. In Section 5, we discuss the relevance of drifting features for *drift detection* by showing that many drift detectors are based on drift intensities. In particular, the algorithm derived in Section 4 can serve as a feature selection method for drift detectors.

of drift intensity from which the notion of drifting features can be derived (Section 3). We then recall the basic notions of information theory-based feature selection (Section 4.1) and study the connection to drifting features (Section 4.2). In particular, we derive a general algorithmic scheme (Algorithm 1) for how to apply classical feature selection algorithms to the concept of drifting features. Furthermore, we analyze the connection between drift intensity and practically used drift detectors, including the choice of meta-parameters, specifically the properties of the windowing schemes and the metric used (Section 5). We then empirically evaluate the resulting algorithm on several benchmarks regarding performance increase in drift detection (Section 6) before concluding the paper (Section 7).

2. Preliminary notes

We start by introducing the notation we will use throughout the paper and recall the fundamentals of concept drift.

2.1. Notations

In the following, we consider a data space \mathcal{X} composed of multiple features. We refer to the index set of all features as \mathbf{F} , $|\mathbf{F}| < \infty$. Every feature $f \in \mathbf{F}$ takes values in the space \mathcal{X}_f and \mathcal{X} is the product $\mathcal{X} = \prod_{f \in \mathbf{F}} \mathcal{X}_f$. We assume that all \mathcal{X}_f are standard Borel spaces, e.g., $\mathcal{X}_f = \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R}^d, [0, 1], \mathbb{N}$, or $\{1, \dots, n\}$. For a subset $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$, $\mathcal{X}_F = \prod_{f \in F} \mathcal{X}_f$ denotes the subspace of features in F . Thus, every \mathcal{X}_F is also a standard Borel space. For $F' \subseteq F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ we denote by $\text{proj}_{F'}^F : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow \mathcal{X}_{F'}$ the projection of the features F onto the subset of features F' . We drop the super-script if no confusion can occur.

For a random variable X with values in \mathcal{X} , we write $X_F = \text{proj}_F X$. For $F_1, \dots, F_n \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ pairwise disjoint and $F = \cup_i F_i$ and a probability measure P on \mathcal{X} , by abuse of notation the marginalization of P onto \mathcal{X}_F is denoted as $P(X_{F_1}, \dots, X_{F_n}) = P \circ (\text{proj}_F)^{-1}$ and $P[X_{F_1} \in A_1, \dots, X_{F_n} \in A_n] = P \circ (\text{proj}_F)^{-1}(A_1 \times \dots \times A_n)$. Analogous notations are used for transition kernels with values in \mathcal{X} , conditional probabilities, etc.

2.2. A statistical framework of concept drift

Let us shortly introduce the notion of learning with drift in contrast to classical batch learning. In classical batch machine learning, one assumes that the data-generating distribution D is time-invariant. In

this scenario, a sample of size n is a collection of n i.i.d. random variables $X_1, \dots, X_n \sim D$.

However, real-world applications such as learning from data streams violate the assumption of a time-invariant distribution. A data point observed at time point $t \in \mathcal{T}$ follows a potentially distinct distribution D_t . Drift refers to observing data from different distributions, i.e., $D_t \neq D_s$ for some $t, s \in \mathcal{T}$ [2,9]. We refer to the mathematical framework introduced in [12] where D_t is sided by a distribution P_T on time \mathcal{T} that describes the likelihood of observing a sample at a given time. Together, P_T and D_t form a *distribution process* (or sometimes *drift process*) [12,14]:

Definition 1. Let $\mathcal{T} = [0, 1]$ and $\mathcal{X} = \mathbb{R}^d$ or, more generally, standard Borel spaces. A (*regular post hoc*) *distribution process* (P_T, D_t) from the *time domain* \mathcal{T} to the *data space* \mathcal{X} is a probability measure P_T on \mathcal{T} together with a Markov kernel D_t from \mathcal{T} to \mathcal{X} , i.e., D_t is a probability measure on \mathcal{X} for all $t \in \mathcal{T}$ and the mapping $t \mapsto D_t(A)$ is measurable for all measurable $A \subseteq \mathcal{X}$.

Let (P_T, D_t) be a distribution process. We say that D_t has *drift* iff the probability of observing different data distributions is larger than zero:

$$P_T^2(\{(t, s) \in \mathcal{T}^2 \mid D_t \neq D_s\}) > 0, \tag{1}$$

where P_T^2 is the product measure of P_T with itself, i.e., the measure on $\mathcal{T} \times \mathcal{T}$ that is uniquely determined by $P_T^2(W_1 \times W_2) = P_T(W_1)P_T(W_2)$ for all measurable $W_1, W_2 \subseteq \mathcal{T}$.

Any algorithm that determines from a given finite set of observations whether there is drift is referred to as a *drift detector*.

We write D_t instead of (P_T, D_t) if this does not lead to confusion. As before, we write $D_t(X_F)$ for the marginal of D_t on \mathcal{X}_F . Note that $(P_T, D_t(X_F))$ is also a distribution process from \mathcal{T} to \mathcal{X}_F .

A distribution process induces two important distributions: we refer to the distribution D on $\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{T}$ which is uniquely determined by the property $D(A \times W) = \int_W D_t(A) dP_T(t)$ for all $A \subseteq \mathcal{X}$, $W \subseteq \mathcal{T}$ as the *holistic distribution* of D_t . A P_T non-null set $W \subseteq \mathcal{T}$ is referred to as *time window* and $D_W(A) = \int D_t(A) dP_T(t \mid W) = D(A \times W \mid \mathcal{X} \times W)$ denotes the *mean distribution* during W . Using these distributions, we can sample from a distribution process: (X, T) is a sample point of D_t if (X, T) is a $\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{T}$ -valued random variable distributed according to the holistic distribution D , i.e., $T \sim P_T$ and $X \mid [T = t] \sim D_t$.

One crucial observation from [12] uniquely characterizes the presence of drift by means of a dependency criterion of data X and time T :

Fig. 2. Visualization of drifting features. Each line corresponds to one feature which is either 1 or -1 , observed over time. The line indicates the moment in which drift occurs. Feature 1 is not drifting, Features 2 to 4 are drifting separately, Features 5 and 6 are not drifting if considered separately but their correlation is affected by drift, the product X_5X_6 is -1 if considered before the drift and 1 after the drift (see [Example 1](#)). The number on the right-hand side refers to the (total variation) drift intensity, a quantity that we introduce to measure individual or group-wise feature drift in this article.

Fig. 3. Visualization of dataset described in [Example 2](#). Left plot shows distribution conditioned on $P = 0$, right distribution conditioned on $P = 1$, time is color and shape-coded ($T \leq 0$). As can be seen for $P = 1$ only X_1 is affected by the drift and thus is drifting, for $P = 0$ the product X_1X_2 is equal to the sign of T and thus X_2 is a drifting feature, too. Yet, if $\mathbb{P}[P = 1] \approx 0$ then considering X_1 only leads to very weak drift.

Theorem 1. Let D_t be a distribution process and (X, T) a sample point from D_t , i.e., $(X, T) \sim D$ is a pair of random variables. Then D_t has drift if and only if data and time are dependent, i.e., $X \not\perp T$.

Yet, this notion of drift is a property of the distribution as a whole and it does not relate to single features. In the following, we are interested in the possibility of attributing the presence of drift to characteristics of single ‘drifting’ features.

3. Drift intensity and drifting features

In this section, we introduce the notion of *drifting features*. In contrast to the notion of drift which refers to the distribution as a whole, this notion focuses on the behavior of single features. Here we address the question “what is the contribution of a single feature or groups of features to the drift?” which is of particular interest to (i) providing insights and explainability of the drift, (ii) enabling targeted remedies, e.g., by recalibrating or removing the affected features. Knowledge of these drifting features is not only relevant for learning with drift [10, 11] but also drift detection [15] and analysis [3, 8, 16].

3.1. Naïve selection strategies

Intuitively, a drifting feature is a feature that, if added to a process, causes drift. Yet naïve strategies which rely on the mere presence or absence of drift if a feature or group of features is removed or added do not suffice to identify drifting features. This is because causes of drift can be superimposed and distributed among groups of features. Here, we highlight this by two examples:

Example 1 (Unsuitability of Selecting Single Features Only). An intuitive way to characterize drifting features would be a feature-wise view: we could call X_f a drifting feature if and only if $D_t(X_f)$ has drift. However, this leads to counterintuitive examples if the drift affects correlations rather than marginal distributions of a single feature. Consider the following simple example, which is visualization in [Fig. 2](#) (Features 5,6):

Let $\mathcal{X} = \{-1, 1\}^2$, $\mathcal{T} = [-1, 1]$, $P_T = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{T})$. Let X_1 be Rademacher, i.e., $\mathbb{P}[X_1 = -1] = \mathbb{P}[X_1 = 1] = 1/2$, and $X_2 = \text{sign}(T)X_1$. Then $\mathbb{P}[X_2 = -1 | T = t] = \mathbb{P}[X_2 = 1 | T = t] = 1/2$ is Rademacher, too, for all t . In particular, neither $D_t(X_1)$ nor $D_t(X_2)$ has drift. However, $X_1X_2 = \text{sign}(T)$ and thus D_t has drift.

Notice that this problem can occur for arbitrary numbers of features and complex distributions. We provide a formalization and proof of this fact in the appendix (see [Lemma 2](#)).

Example 2 (Unsuitability of Considering Minimal Drift-Inducing Sets). As an alternative, one can consider all feature sets such that their joint distribution has drift and that are minimal with respect to set inclusion. Drifting features are all features that are contained in any such minimal set. Here, the minimality is necessary as $D_t(X_{F'})$ having drift implies $D_t(X_F)$ having drift for all $F' \subseteq F$. Yet, this specification misses relevant features, since drift can happen as a superposition. Consider the following example which is visualized in [Fig. 3](#):

Let $\mathcal{X} = \{-1, 0, 1\}^2$, $\mathcal{T} = [-1, 1]$, $P_T = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{T})$, and $p \in (0, 1)$. Let $T \sim P_T$, ε be Rademacher, i.e., $\mathbb{P}[\varepsilon = -1] = \mathbb{P}[\varepsilon = 1] = 1/2$, $P \sim \text{Ber}(p)$ be Bernoulli with mean p , i.e., $\mathbb{P}[P = 1] = 1 - \mathbb{P}[P = 0] = p$, and all independent. Consider $X_2 = \varepsilon(1 - P)$ and $X_1 = \text{sign}(T)(X_2 + P)$.

For $P = 0$ we have $X_2 = \varepsilon$, $X_1 = \text{sign}(T)\varepsilon$. So no single random variable has drift, but $X_1 \cdot X_2 = \text{sign}(T)$ so D_t has drift. For $P = 1$ we have $X_2 = 0$ and $X_1 = \text{sign}(T)$.

Now set $W = [-1, 0)$, $W' = (0, 1]$ and let X' be a copy of X and assume that X was observed before and X' after 0, i.e., we condition on $T \in W$, $T' \in W'$ or equivalently $T < 0 < T'$. For clarity write $\tilde{\mathbb{P}} = \mathbb{P}[\cdot | T \in W, T' \in W']$ for the conditional. Then we have

$$\tilde{\mathbb{P}}[X_1 \neq X'_1] = \tilde{\mathbb{P}}[X_1 \neq X'_1 | P = 1]p + \tilde{\mathbb{P}}[X_1 \neq X'_1 | P = 0](1 - p) \quad (2)$$

$$= \tilde{\mathbb{P}}[-1 \neq 1]p + \tilde{\mathbb{P}}[-\varepsilon \neq \varepsilon'](1 - p) \quad (3)$$

so X_1 is a minimal drifting set. Therefore, given that X_2 alone is not drifting, X_2 is not contained in any minimal drifting set. However, taking the discriminatory power as measured by the total variation d_{TV} into account we observe

$$d_{\text{TV}}(D_W(X_1), D_{W'}(X_1)) = 2 \inf_{\substack{X \sim D_W \\ X' \sim D_{W'}}} \mathbb{P}[X_1 \neq X'_1] = 2p \quad (4)$$

as $-\varepsilon$ is again Rademacher and thus $-\varepsilon$ and ε' follow the same distribution. In contrast, if we consider X_1 and X_2 we obtain

$$\tilde{\mathbb{P}}[X \neq X'] = \tilde{\mathbb{P}}[X \neq X' | P = 1]p + \tilde{\mathbb{P}}[X \neq X' | P = 0](1 - p) \quad (5)$$

$$\geq \tilde{\mathbb{P}}[X_1 \neq X'_1 | P = 1]p + \tilde{\mathbb{P}}[X_1X_2 \neq X'_1X'_2 | P = 0](1 - p) \quad (6)$$

$$= \tilde{\mathbb{P}}[-1 \neq 1]p + \tilde{\mathbb{P}}[-1 \neq 1](1 - p) = 1 \quad (7)$$

$$\Rightarrow d_{\text{TV}}(D_W, D_{W'}) = 2 \inf_{\substack{X \sim D_W \\ X' \sim D_{W'}}} \tilde{\mathbb{P}}[X \neq X'] = 2. \quad (8)$$

So we see that considering both X_1 and X_2 allows stable drift detection while drift detection based on X_1 approaches random chance as $p \rightarrow 0$.

This example can be extended to more complex distributions and more intricate drift effects similar to Lemma 2, displaying the complexity of the challenge to identify sets of drifting features.

3.2. (Kullback–Leibler) Drift intensity

In the following, we propose an efficient way to resolve the problems discussed in Section 3.1 by introducing quantitative values which, rather than only asking whether or not $D_t(X_F)$ is drifting, quantify the increase of the drift when adding the features $F \setminus F'$. More specifically, we introduce the *drift intensity* as a suitable scoring function.

Conceptually, for a fixed distribution process a drift intensity I_{D_t} assigns a real number to each set of features $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ such that the following two requirements hold:

1. I_{D_t} is monotonic, i.e., $I_{D_t}(F') \leq I_{D_t}(F)$ for all $F' \subseteq F$. This corresponds to the statement that if $D_t(X_{F'})$ has drift then so does $D_t(X_F)$.
2. If F does not provide more information on the drift than $F' \subseteq F$, then I_{D_t} does not increase.

The challenge is how to quantify the notion of “more information on the drift”. As a motivation, we start with the definition of drift. As discussed in [12], the presence of drift is equivalent to the fact that time point-specific distribution $D_t(X_F)$ is different from the global mean distribution $D_{\mathcal{T}}(X_F)$ on a P_T non-null set. That means, the following integral:

$$P_T(\{t \in \mathcal{T} \mid D_t(X_F) \neq D_{\mathcal{T}}(X_F)\}) = \int \mathbf{1}[D_t(X_F) \neq D_{\mathcal{T}}(X_F)] dP_T(t) \quad (9)$$

does not vanish. Yet, this quantity faces similar problems as the minimal-set approach discussed in Example 2 because it refers to the discrete observation of whether two distributions are identical or not. An intuitive solution is to replace the discrete value $\mathbf{1}[D_t(X_F) \neq D_{\mathcal{T}}(X_F)]$ by a (continuous) distance measure. One popular choice from the literature is offered by the Kullback–Leibler divergence, leading to the following definition:

Definition 2. Let D_t be a distribution process. The *Kullback–Leibler drift intensity* is defined as

$$I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(F) = \int D_{\text{KL}}(D_t(X_F) \parallel D_{\mathcal{T}}(X_F)) dP_T(t). \quad (10)$$

where D_{KL} denotes the Kullback–Leibler divergence.

This measure quantifies, how well the mean distribution $D_{\mathcal{T}}(X_F)$ approximates the time point specific distribution $D_t(X_F)$ on average. Fig. 2 displays the drift intensity of different feature sets of sizes one and two in one example.

The Kullback–Leibler drift intensity has desirable mathematical properties: it has been shown that the Kullback–Leibler divergence is monotonous w.r.t. set inclusion. By monotonicity of integrals, it follows that the Kullback–Leibler drift intensity is also monotonic. Furthermore, $D_{\text{KL}}(D_t(X_F) \parallel D_{\mathcal{T}}(X_F)) = 0$ if and only if $D_t(X_F) = D_{\mathcal{T}}(X_F)$. Hence, it is easy to see that the drift intensity is larger than 0 if and only if $D_t(X_F)$ has drift. This implies that the Kullback–Leibler drift intensity is a valid measure based on which drift detection can be performed. A formal proof of this statement is part of Lemma 1.

However, here, we consider the more general question under which conditions an increase of Kullback–Leibler drift intensity is strict, i.e., for which $D_t, F' \subseteq F$ do we have $I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(F') < I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(F)$. The formalization relies on conditioning for distribution processes. In the literature, this has been used to define real drift, i.e., a change of the decision rule: $D_t(Y \mid X) \neq D_s(Y \mid X)$ with data X and label Y . This notion can be adapted to the statistical framework of [12] as shown in [17]. Rather than a distinct label, we target the prediction of additional features $X_{F \setminus F'}$ based on the already considered ones $X_{F'}$. Extending [17], this leads to the notion of conditional drift as follows:

Definition 3. Let D_t be a distribution process on \mathcal{X} and (X, T) be a sample point drawn from D_t , i.e., $(X, T) \sim D$ is a pair of random variables. For $F, F' \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ we say that X_F has conditional drift given $X_{F'}$ if and only if $X_F \not\perp T \mid X_{F'}$.

From a model point of view, conditional drift expresses the idea that drift affects the prediction of X_F from $X_{F'}$:

Proposition 1. Let D_t be a distribution process and $F' \subseteq F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$. X_F has no conditional drift given $X_{F'}$ if and only if $D_t(X_F)$ factors as $D_{\mathcal{T}}(X_F \mid X_{F'})D_t(X_{F'})$.

Proof. All proofs can be found in the appendix. \square

Using the notion of conditional drift we can exactly characterize under which circumstances the Kullback–Leibler drift intensity increases:

Lemma 1. Let D_t be a distribution process and $(X, T) \sim D$ a sample point. The Kullback–Leibler drift intensity is monotonic with respect to set inclusion, i.e., for $F' \subseteq F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ we have

$$0 = I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(\emptyset) \leq I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(F') \stackrel{(*)}{\leq} I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(F) \leq I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(\mathbf{F}). \quad (11)$$

Equality holds in $(*)$ if and only if X_F has no conditional drift given $X_{F'}$. In particular, $I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(F) = 0$ if and only if $D_t(X_F)$ has no drift and $I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(\mathbf{F}) = 0$ if and only if D_t has no drift.

3.3. Total variation drift intensity

Instead of using Kullback–Leibler divergence to derive a drift intensity, we can also make use of total variation which leads to

$$I_{D_t, \text{TV}}(F) = \iint d_{\text{TV}}(D_t(X_F), D_s(X_F)) dP_T(t) dP_T(s), \quad (12)$$

here we start from the pairwise comparison $\mathbf{1}[D_t \neq D_s]$ which corresponds directly to Definition 1 by taking the double integral.

Note that the inner term $d_{\text{TV}}(D_t(X_F), D_s(X_F))$ is also referred to as drift magnitude in the literature and studied intensely in [3,18], for example. It is interesting to observe that there is a natural relation between the total variation norm and popular drift detectors from the literature that are based on virtual classifiers [19,20] such as D3 [21], MMD [22,23], or the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test [24], etc. These drift detectors rely on tests of the classification performance being better than random guessing [14]. Since the total variation is a tight upper bound for the accuracy of the optimal binary classifier, this connection allows to relate properties of the total variation drift intensity and the statistics of the respective drift detectors. We will discuss this aspect further in Section 5.

Similar to the Kullback–Leibler drift intensity the total variation drift intensity is monotonic, sends the empty set to 0, and takes on values larger 0 if and only if $D_t(X_F)$ has drift. Hence both drift intensities show similar behavior.

3.4. Drifting features

As stated before, a drifting feature is a feature that contributes to the drift. Based on the notion of drift intensity to quantify the amount of drift, we arrive at a key formalization proposed in this article: we characterize drifting features as those features that change the drift intensity, formally:

Definition 4. Let D_t be a distribution process with features \mathbf{F} . We say that $f \in \mathbf{F}$ is a *drifting feature* or that the feature f is *drifting* (w.r.t. Kullback–Leibler) iff it can increase the (Kullback–Leibler) drift intensity, i.e., there is $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ such that

$$I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(F) < I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(F \cup \{f\}). \quad (13)$$

We denote the set of all drifting features (w.r.t. Kullback–Leibler) by $R_{\text{KL}}(\mathcal{D}_I)$, i.e.,

$$R_{\text{KL}}(\mathcal{D}_I) = \{f \in \mathbf{F} \mid \exists F \subseteq \mathbf{F} : I_{\mathcal{D}_I, \text{KL}}(F) < I_{\mathcal{D}_I, \text{KL}}(F \cup \{f\})\}, \quad (14)$$

A feature that is not drifting is called a *non-drifting feature* (w.r.t. Kullback–Leibler). The set of non-drifting features is denoted by $N_{\text{KL}}(\mathcal{D}_I) = \mathbf{F} \setminus R_{\text{KL}}(\mathcal{D}_I)$.

Notice that we can make the same definition based on the total variation drift intensity, however, in general, this leads to a different set of drifting features.

The definition of drifting features fulfills several desired properties (formalization and proofs are provided in the appendix):

1. Non-drifting features do not contain any information on the drift. Drifting features remain relevant and cannot be shadowed even if more information becomes available (see Proposition 5).
2. If a distribution process has drift then there exists a drifting feature (compare to Example 1). Conversely, if there is no drift then there does not exist a drifting feature (see Proposition 6).
3. Data processing does not create drift, i.e., given observations of non-drifting features, and a potentially randomized processing operation/algorithm A which does not take time information into account, then the output of A does not induce new drifting features and in particular has no drift itself (see Proposition 7).
4. The drift intensities assign scores to sets of features. We can use generic game-theoretic concepts, more precisely the so-called Shapley values, to derive induced scores, which compute the unique contribution of every single feature to these coalitions [25]. These values quantify the individual feature relevance for the drift intensity. We have that a value is larger than 0 if and only if the feature is drifting (see Proposition 8).

3.5. Axioms of drift intensities

So far, we have introduced two notions of drift intensity and demonstrated that these formal definitions lead to desirable properties concerning the characterization of drifting features. Before targeting the challenge of finding drifting features algorithmically in Section 4, we generalize the notion of drift intensity to allow other metrics.

Besides the Kullback–Leibler divergence and total variation, measures such as the Wasserstein distance are of interest for certain applications due to their geometric interpretation. Moreover, many drift detectors are based on metrics derived from models and are thus not addressed. To obtain an adequately rich notion of metrics, it is reasonable not to require that drift intensity increases if and only if the added feature is conditionally drifting. Here, even the “only if” part would be too restrictive (see Example 3). The same holds for the condition that adding non-drifting features (with respect to Kullback–Leibler drift intensity) does not increase the intensity (see Example 4) unless they are completely unrelated to the remaining features. These strict conditions mirror the fact that independence is defined in the context of all possible functions. In practice, it is reasonable to restrict to specific model classes, leading to weaker axioms.

We thus arrive at the following formal definition, which subsumes and generalizes the notions of drift intensity as introduced above:

Definition 5. A *drift intensity* I on a standard Borel space \mathcal{X} with features \mathbf{F} is a function $I : \Pr(\mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{T}) \times \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{F}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that for every distribution process¹ \mathcal{D}_I and for $F' \subseteq F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$, it holds that $I_{\mathcal{D}_I}$

1. is non-negative, i.e., $I_{\mathcal{D}_I}(\emptyset) = 0$
2. is monotonic, i.e., $I_{\mathcal{D}_I}(F') \leq I_{\mathcal{D}_I}(F)$

¹ Here we use that on a standard Borel space a distribution process uniquely corresponds to its holistic distribution.

3. does not wrongly detect drift, i.e., if $I_{\mathcal{D}_I}(F') < I_{\mathcal{D}_I}(F)$ then $X_{F \setminus F'} \not\perp X_{F, T}$.

For every drift intensity I , we obtain a notion of drifting features by replacing the Kullback–Leibler drift intensity in Definition 4 by I . Unlike before, however, extreme instantiations of drift intensities can lead to notions of drifting features that suffer from the same issues as the ones discussed in Section 3.1. We give three examples:

- *0-drift intensity:* $I_{\mathcal{D}_I, 0}(F) = 0$ is a valid drift intensity, yet, the set of drifting features is always empty.
- *feature-wise drift intensity:* $I(F) = \sum_{f \in F} \mathbf{1}[D_I(X_f) \text{ has drift}]$ leads to the feature-wise notion of drifting features addressed by Example 1.
- *minimal-set drift intensity:* $I(F) = \mathbf{1}[D_I(X_F) \text{ has drift}]$ leads to the minimal-set notion of drifting features addressed by Example 2.

Hence the specific properties induced by a drift intensity need to be carefully checked as they might be subject to insufficiencies of the respective notions of drifting features, such as limited sensitivity to drift in correlations and drift strength. We will study the properties for different drift intensities that are particularly relevant for practical applications more closely in Section 5.2.

4. Connection to feature selection

In this section, we aim for efficient methods to compute or approximate drifting features. For this purpose, we explore a link to feature selection technologies. We start with a short summary of the classical theory of feature relevance for classification or regression problems. Then, we extend it to the notion of drifting features developed in the last section and derive an algorithm based on these considerations.

4.1. Feature relevance for learning models

Assume a classification or regression problems with data space \mathcal{X} and label space \mathcal{Y} ($\mathcal{Y} = \{0, \dots, n\}$ or $\mathcal{Y} = \mathbb{R}$). We consider pairs of random variables (X, Y) . Following [26], a feature X_f is dubbed relevant for the prediction of the label Y if it provides information regarding Y . As the information in X_f can be inaccessible without information from other features (see [27, Theorem 13]) we have to take additional features X_F into account. Thus, for binary classification, we arrive at

$$\mathbb{P}_{x \sim \mathbb{P}_X} [P[Y = 1 \mid X_f = x_f, X_F = x_F] \neq P[Y = 1 \mid X_F = x_F]] > 0 \quad (15)$$

where $P[Y = 1 \mid \cdot]$ is the Bayes-optimal classifier. Yet, the additional information can also make X_f uninformative for the prediction, e.g., if X_F contains a copy of X_f , so we have to consider all possible F . More formally and generally, we can express this idea in terms of conditional independence:

Definition 6. A feature f is *relevant* to Y if and only if there exists a (potentially empty) set $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ such that X_f and Y are not independent given X_F , i.e.

$$Y \not\perp X_f \mid X_F. \quad (16)$$

A feature that is not relevant is called *irrelevant*. The problem of finding all features that are relevant to the prediction of Y is referred to as the *all-relevant problem*, i.e., the solution to the all-relevant problem is given by the set

$$R(Y \mid X_{\mathbf{F}}) = \{f \in \mathbf{F} \mid X_f \text{ is relevant to } Y\}. \quad (17)$$

4.2. Determining drifting features efficiently

We can link the notion of feature relevance to the notion of drifting features as follows:

Fig. 4. Four stage model of drift detection.

Algorithm 1 Select Drifting Features.

-
- 1: **Input:** $S = \{(x_1, t_1), \dots, (x_n, t_n)\}$ dated datapoints
 - 2: **Output:** R set of drifting features
 - 3: $S' \leftarrow \text{PREPROCESS}(S) \{S' = \{(x_i, f(t_i)) \mid (x_i, t_i) \in S\}\}$
 - 4: $R \leftarrow \text{FEATURESELECTION}(S')$
 - 5: **return** R
-

Theorem 2. Let D_t be a distribution process with features \mathbf{F} . Let (X, T) be a sample point drawn from D_t , i.e., $(X, T) \sim D$ is a pair of random variables. A feature f is drifting (in the sense of Kullback–Leibler) if and only if X_f is relevant to T . The set of all drifting features is given by a solution of the all-relevant problem for T , i.e., $R_{\text{KL}}(D_t) = R(T \mid X_F)$.

As a consequence, a large variety of algorithms for determining drifting features becomes available as this can be done by feature selection for the mapping $X \rightarrow T$. Yet, the all-relevant problem is NP-hard [27]. Furthermore, many popular algorithmic solutions for feature selection and the all-relevant problem are not suited for our setup since they deal with classification tasks with discrete labels or real-valued cost functions such as MSE, which do not carry enough information [7]. In contrast, we deal with T as a continuous random variable and the whole conditional distribution needs to be taken into account.

Hence we resort to ideas that have been introduced in [7]: the problem of conditional density estimation can be turned into a multi-regression problem via suitable pre-processing of the output value [28, 29]. Common transformations are as follows:

- *Discretization* $y \mapsto \sum_{i=1}^n 2^i \mathbb{1}[y \in W_i]$ turns the problem into a classification problem, approximating $\mathbb{P}_{T|X}$ by piecewise constant functions (here $W_1, \dots, W_n \subseteq \mathcal{T}$).
- *Fourier transform* $y \mapsto (\exp(-2\pi i k y))_{k=-d}^d$ approximates the Fourier transform of $\mathbb{P}_{T|X}$ up to degree d (here $\mathcal{T} = [-1, 1]$).
- *Higher moments* $y \mapsto (x^k)_{k=1}^d$ approximate $\mathbb{P}_{T|X}$ by a polynomial (here $\mathcal{T} = [-1, 1]$).

In the case of discretization with $n = 2$, this process is also referred to as drift localization [30], in all other cases it is referred to as drift segmentation [31]. Thus, this procedure for determining the drifting features constitutes an instance of the more general scheme of model-based drift explanations as introduced in [5,8].

The resulting pseudo-code which enables the identifying of drifting features based on a label transformation $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ is presented in Algorithm 1. Note that in step 4 `FEATURESELECTION` might resort to a parametric model which is fitted for the set S' [6,32,33], or it might proceed in a non-parametric way based on the preprocessed data only [34,35].

5. Using drift intensity for drift detection

So far our considerations mainly focused on drift intensity and the explanatory value that can be derived when identifying drifting features. In this section, we will discuss the relevance of drift intensity for drift detection and the impact of architectural choices within the

pipeline. More specifically, most drift detectors proceed in a 4-stage fashion [9,14] (see Fig. 4), with stages 2 and 3 corresponding to the estimation of a drift intensity or variation thereof, while stage 1 refers to data collection and 4 to noise and variance control, e.g., the computation of p -values.

This pipeline crucially depends on two choices: the choice of metric in steps 2 and 3 which we discuss in Section 5.2. And the collection of data, i.e., the choice of the window in step 1, whose influence we address in Section 5.1.

5.1. On the effect of the window

The Kullback–Leibler drift intensity compares the distributions D_t for every single time point t . As this is impractical for real applications, most algorithms for drift detection only compare the distributions on time windows D_W . As an inappropriate window can make the drift vanish, see for example [18], the question on the influence of different windows on the detectable drifts and thus drifting features arises. More precisely:

1. If there is drift, does there always exist a pair of windows for which we can observe this drift?
2. Conversely, if drift occurs for one choice of windows, is the drift present in the underlying process?
3. If drift can be observed, do there exist simple windows that can easily be realized within an algorithm in which it is observed? If so, which specific choices of such windows lead to desired results?

The first two questions constitute a sanity check and the answer to both questions is positive. The last question addresses the fact that, rather than arbitrary and possibly complex windows, algorithms typically resort to simple choices such as time intervals. Yet it is unclear, which types of drift can be observed based on which windows.

Let us address the first question. Intuitively, we observe some type of drift between two time windows if the probability of some event differs between the two windows. We specify this by fixating an outcome A , e.g., a certain class, for the observed features X_F , and we fixate a possible conditioning B for features $X_{F'}$ for the observation:

$$D_{W_1}[X_F \in A \mid X_{F'} \in B] \neq D_{W_2}[X_F \in A \mid X_{F'} \in B]. \quad (18)$$

Here, the drift is specified by the usage of A and B and the feature sets F, F' . In this situation, we say that the sets W_1, W_2 witness the drift of A given B . Yet, we need to avoid sets of measure zero as discussed in [17]. Therefore, we multiply both sides by $D[X_{F'} \in B, T \in W_1]D[X_{F'} \in B, T \in W_2]$ which leads to the following:

Definition 7. Let D_t be a distribution process, $(X, T) \sim D$, $W_1, W_2 \subseteq \mathcal{T}$ be time windows, $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ ($\emptyset \neq F' \subseteq \mathbf{F}$) and $A \subseteq \mathcal{X}_F$ ($B \subseteq \mathcal{X}_{F'}$). We say that W_1, W_2 witness the (conditional) drift at A (given B) or are witnessing windows of the (conditional) drift at A (given B) iff²

$$\mathbb{P}[X_F \in A, X_{F'} \in B, T \in W_1] \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in B, T \in W_2] \quad (19)$$

² For unconditional drift we choose $F' = \mathbf{F}$ and $B = \mathcal{X}$

$$\neq \mathbb{P}[X_F \in A, X_{F'} \in B, T \in W_2] \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in B, T \in W_1].$$

We say that W_1, W_2 witness the (conditional) drift iff they witness some (conditional) drift, i.e., there exist A (and B) such that W_1, W_2 witness the (conditional) drift of A (given B).

To address question three: the suitability of specific windows depends on the drift detector and the geometry of \mathcal{T} . We assume that windows can be chosen in some set B_0 which is sufficiently rich. Specifically, we use the concept of an intersection stable generator of the σ -algebra. This is a rather weak restriction subsuming important cases: for $\mathcal{T} = \mathbb{R}$ we may choose all intervals of the form $B_0 = \{(-\infty, t] \mid t \in \mathcal{T}\}$ or $B_0 = \{(t-l, t+l) \mid t \in \mathcal{T}, l \leq \Delta\}$, for example.

This specification allows an answer to the questions in the affirmative, whereby we can resort to popular choices of the window pairs:

Theorem 3. *Let B_0 be an intersection stable generator of the σ -algebra of \mathcal{T} . The following are equivalent:*

1. $X_{F'}$ is conditional drifting given X_F .
2. There is a time window $W \in B_0$ such that W, \mathcal{T} witness the conditional drift of $X_{F'}$ given X_F .
3. There is a time window $W \in B_0$ such that W, W^C witness the conditional drift of $X_{F'}$ given X_F .
4. There are disjoint time windows W_1, W_2 with $W_1, W_2^C \in B_0$ such that W_1, W_2 witness the conditional drift of $X_{F'}$ given X_F .
5. If B_0 contains a countable cover of \mathcal{T} , i.e., $\exists B_i \in B_0 : \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} B_i = \mathcal{T}$, then there are time windows $W_1, W_2, W_3 \in B_0$ such that W_1, W_2 and $W_1, W_3 \setminus W_1$ or $W_1 \setminus W_3, W_3$ witness the conditional drift of $X_{F'}$ given X_F .
6. There are time windows W_1, W_2 that witness the conditional drift of $X_{F'}$ given X_F .

In all cases above we always witness the same A (and B).

Hence, specific choices of typical windows have no major effect on which drift can be detected. Answering questions one to three. However, it is important to notice that the choice of window affects how pronounced the observed drift is. In particular, different windows might lead to the identification of different most prominent drift events (see Example 5). Furthermore, it may happen that a specific drifting feature is not relevant for a specific window, but another one only (see Example 6).

5.2. On the effect of the metric

Other effects are caused by the metric. Indeed, depending on the metric certain drifts can become invisible so that a feature that is relevant on a window for one metric is not relevant to another and vice versa. As many important metrics are derived from function classes the effects discussed above become crucial (see Example 5). Here, we are interested in the relation of the choice of the metric, the validity of the induced drift intensity, and relevant drifting features. We consider the following two questions:

1. Which metrics lead to a valid drift intensity?
2. When and how do the drifting features of the drift intensity induced by a metric relate to those of the Kullback–Leibler drift intensity?

The two major types of metrics used for drift detection are f -divergences and integral probability metrics (IPM). f -divergences are generalizations of the Kullback–Leibler divergence based on a convex function f with $f(1) = 0$. Given a dominating base measure μ and densities p and q of the probability measures P and Q , respectively, the f -divergence is given by

$$D_f(P \parallel Q) = \int_{q>0} q(x) f\left(\frac{p(x)}{q(x)}\right) d\mu(x) + f'(\infty) P[q=0]. \quad (20)$$

where $f'(\infty) = \lim_{x \searrow 0} x f(1/x)$.

Various approaches refer to f -divergences: total variation [3], Hellinger distance [36,37], Jensen–Shannon metric [38], Kullback–Leibler divergence [13,39]. As f -divergences are rather similar they lead to similar sets of drifting features:

Proposition 2. *Let D_f be a f -divergence, then $I_{D_f, D_f}(F) = \int D_f(\mathcal{D}_t(X_F) \parallel \mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{T}}(X_F)) dP_{\mathcal{T}}(t)$ is a drift intensity. Furthermore, the drifting features induced by this drift intensity are a subset of those induced by the Kullback–Leibler drift intensity.*

Despite these similarities, the estimation process can have a significant impact [15].

Another popular class of metrics is IPMs. These check how well functions from a defining class \mathcal{F} can distinguish the two distributions:

$$d_{\mathcal{F}}(P, Q) = \sup_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \left| \int f(x) dP(x) - \int f(x) dQ(x) \right|. \quad (21)$$

An estimator for $d_{\mathcal{F}}$ can be based on the equivalent expression with distribution $(X, Y) \sim \frac{1}{2}(P \times \delta_1 + Q \times \delta_{-1})$:

$$d_{\mathcal{F}}(P, Q) = 2 \sup_{f \in \mathcal{F}} |\mathbb{E}[Y f(X)]|. \quad (22)$$

If the functions in \mathcal{F} take values 1 and -1 only, then $\frac{1}{2}(1 + \mathbb{E}[Y f(X)])$ is simply the accuracy of f and $d_{\mathcal{F}}$ thus relates to the performance of the theoretical best model predicting $X \mapsto Y$.

Several approaches make use of IPMs: total variation norm [3], MMD [22,23], model loss [21,22], Wasserstein metric [8,15,40], conditional mean and moment differences [8,15,41]. Furthermore, by extending the underlying space and using the variational representation, also f -divergences can be considered as IPMs.

In the remainder of this section, we will mainly focus on IPMs where \mathcal{F} is given by machine learning models. Instead of relating them to Kullback–Leibler divergence directly, we will use total variation, which is the only IPM that is also a f -divergence, as an intermediate step. Let us first specify the setup:

Definition 8. Assume a function class of measurable functions \mathcal{F} from some measurable space X to \mathbb{R} is given. The (\mathcal{F} -induced) integral probability metric (IPM) is defined as

$$d_{\mathcal{F}}(P, Q) = \sup_{f \in \mathcal{F}} \left| \int f dP - \int f dQ \right| \quad (23)$$

for probability measures P and Q on X .

For a space \mathcal{X} with features \mathbf{F} a function type / model type is a family of function classes $(\mathcal{F}(F))_{F \subseteq \mathbf{F}}$, such that $\mathcal{F}(F)$ is a function class on \mathcal{X}_F for each $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$. For a function type \mathcal{F} and a distribution process \mathcal{D} , with $\mathcal{T} = \{W_1, W_2\}$ we refer to

$$I_{\mathcal{D}, \mathcal{F}}(F) = \begin{cases} d_{\mathcal{F}(F)}(\mathcal{D}_{W_1}(X_F), \mathcal{D}_{W_2}(X_F)) & \text{if } F \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

as the \mathcal{F} -induced drift intensity.

We start by discussing which model types induce IPMs that lead to valid drift intensities. The key observation is that the IPM of a model class of classifiers has a very natural interpretation: it yields the best possible accuracy for the task of classifying data points from a stream as either happening before or after the drift event. Validity of drift intensities corresponds to the property that the class of models type does not shrink for more features, i.e., $\mathcal{F}(F') \hookrightarrow \mathcal{F}(F)$ is an embedding, and that no new functions are induced by restricting to marginals, i.e., $f \in \mathcal{F}(F)$ then $f(\cdot, x) \in \mathcal{F}(F')$ for $x \in \mathcal{X}_{F \setminus F'}$.

Proposition 3. *Let \mathcal{F} be a model type on \mathcal{X} of bounded functions. The \mathcal{F} -induced drift intensity is a drift intensity, i.e., $I_{\mathcal{F}}$ fulfills Definition 5, if the following holds for all $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}, f \in \mathcal{F}$:*

1. models in $\mathcal{F}(F)$ can be approximated by models in $\mathcal{F}(F \cup \{f\})$, i.e., for all $h_1 \in \mathcal{F}(F)$, $\varepsilon > 0$, and probability measures P on $\mathcal{X}_{F \cup \{f\}}$, there exists a $h_2 \in \mathcal{F}(F \cup \{f\})$ such that $\|h_1 \circ \text{proj}_F - h_2\|_{L^1(P)} < \varepsilon$, and
2. axis-aligned slices of models in $\mathcal{F}(F \cup \{f\})$ can be approximated by models in $\mathcal{F}(F)$, i.e., for all $h_2 \in \mathcal{F}(F \cup \{f\})$, $x \in \mathcal{X}_f$, $\varepsilon > 0$, and probability measures P on \mathcal{X}_F , there exists a $h_1 \in \mathcal{F}(F)$ such that $\|h_2(\cdot, x) - h_1\|_{L^2(P)} < \varepsilon$.

These two requirements hold for many popular models including k -NN, RBF networks, kernel methods, prototype-based models, decision trees, linear models, or neural networks. It follows immediately, that the statistic of the Kolmogorov Smirnov (KS) test [24], which is the IPM of axis-aligned linear models, is a valid drift intensity. Also, the accuracy of many other models like linear models, RBF networks, neural networks, k -NN, random forests, etc. are valid drift intensities. Yet, they are not all equally sensitive to different types of drift. For example, KS is not capable of detecting drift in correlations. Linear models can detect (unconditional) drift [15] but may miss conditional drifts [17] (see Example 3). It is therefore an interesting question which models lead to the same drifting features as the total variation drift intensity. The following result states that models lead to the same drifting features if they are universal:

Proposition 4. *Let F be a model type. If one of the following holds*

1. F consists of binary classifiers $f : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ and is universal w.r.t accuracy, i.e., for all $g : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$, $\varepsilon > 0$, and P there exists $f \in F$ such that $\mathbb{P}_{X \sim P}[g(X) = f(X)] > 1 - \varepsilon$.
2. F contains probabilistic binary classifier $f : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and is universal w.r.t cross-entropy, i.e., for all Lipschitz continuous compactly supported $g : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $\varepsilon > 0$, and P there exists f such that $\mathbb{E}_{X \sim P}[D_{\text{KL}}(g(X) \| f(X))] < \varepsilon$.
3. F contains binary classifiers of the form $f(x) = \text{sign}(h(x))$, and the model-functions $h : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are universal w.r.t L^1 -approximation, i.e., for all compactly supported Lipschitz continuous $g : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow [-1, 1]$, $\varepsilon > 0$, and P there exists h such that $\|g - h\|_{L^1(P)} < \varepsilon$.

then a feature is drifting w.r.t. F if and only if it is drifting w.r.t. total variation. In particular, the F -induced drift intensity is a drift intensity (in the sense of Definition 5).

As a consequence of this proposition, tree-, binning-, and neighbor-based methods lead to the same drifting features as the total variation.

In conclusion, we have seen that typical drift detection schemes are based on drift intensities. In particular, using Propositions 2 and 3 it is easy to verify that the following approaches are indeed based on drift intensities [3,8,15,15,21–24,36–39,42]. Furthermore, using Propositions 2 and 4 we see that the drift intensities used by [3,8,15,22,37–39] are related to those of the Kullback–Leibler drift intensity which can efficiently be found using Algorithm 1.

6. Experiment – Feature selection for drift detection

We accompany these theoretical results with empirical evidence, putting a focus on the effect of restrictions to drifting features on the performance of drift detectors. More specifically, we quantitatively evaluate the performance of drift detectors under restrictions on drifting features, thereby comparing different possible pipelines for several benchmark datasets.³

³ The experimental code is available at <https://github.com/FabianHinder/Feature-based-Analyses-of-Concept-Drift>.

Datasets. We use the following benchmark base datasets “Electricity market prices” (Electricity) [43], “Forest Covertype” (Forest) [44], “Nebraska Weather” (Weather) [45], “HTTP”, “Credit Card”, “Agrawal”, “SEA”, “Mixed” [46]. The datasets are selected to have a broad variation of different types of drift, this includes the domain (weather, finance, cyber security, theoretical/synthetic), the problem (classification, regression, anomaly detection), the feature type (numeric, discrete, mixed), the number of features, and the problem complexity. We sample 100 or 250 data points in total with a single abrupt drift at 0% (no drift), 10%, 25%, and 50% of the data sample. Unwanted drift is removed by randomly permuting the samples before and after the drift [15].

To explore the effect of feature selection, we consider a different number of non-drifting features that are added to the already existing features. We always keep all original features unchanged. The non-drifting features are generated by randomly choosing features from the original dataset and then permuting them over the whole time (cf. shadow features [6]). We consider two versions: we either use the same permutation for all added features to keep the correlations between them, or we use a different permutation for each feature to destroy correlations. We consider 0-250 additional features.

We end up with 1,920 different dataset setups. Each of the dataset setups is independently sampled and repeated 200 times.

Selection method. We apply the feature selection directly to the samples without any pre-processing.

For those feature selection methods that require machine learning models, we consider the following: k -Nearest Neighbor (k -NN), Random Forest (RF), Extra Tree (ET), Decision Tree (DT; cls only), Ridge Regression (Ridge; reg only), and Logistic Regression (Lin; cls only). According to Section 4.2 we use two pre-processing of T : discretization with two time windows, i.e., binary classification (cls; assumed change point at 50%) and Fourier transform (reg; degree $d = 5$), i.e., multi-regression.

We use the following algorithms for feature selection: Boruta [6] (RF, ET; use statistic for ranking), Recursive Feature Elimination [32] (RFE; RF, ET, Lin), Permutation Feature Importance [33] (PFI; all models), native Feature Importance (FI; RF, ET), Mutual Information [34, 35] (MI; based on k -NN).

We compare these methods to two types of baselines: (i) considering all features (all) and (ii) dimensionality reduction/(random) projection schemes: PCA, Gaussian random projection [22] (GRP), Uniform random projection [15] (URP), Sparse random projection [22] (SRP).

Drift detection schemes. For the final step, we consider the following drift detection schemes: Kolmogorov Smirnov test (KS), MMD with Gauss kernel, D3 with k -Nearest Neighbor (k -NN), Decision Tree (DT), and Logistic Regression (Lin). For each detector, we always use 50% of the sample as the assumed moment of drift. In each experimental run, we first generate the datasets as described before, and then perform the feature selection. Based on the obtained set of features, we perform drift detection and document the drift scores, e.g., statistics, p -values, etc. We visualized some cases in Fig. 5.

Afterward, we compare the drift scores obtained from the detector on streams with and without drift using the ROC–AUC. This way our results are not affected by insufficient choices of the decision threshold. To further reduce complexity, we plot the obtained ROC–AUC against the number of additional features and consider the AUC of the resulting diagram (see Fig. 6 for an example visualization). This value serves as our main score. We report the mean rank over all experiments in Fig. 7.

We end up with 183×5 pipelines (select+detection) in total.

Results. The following is a summary of the $1920 \times 183 \times 5 \approx 1,800,000$ distinct experimental setups. For each, we performed 200 independent runs.

Considering the mean rankings across all datasets and drift detectors which are visualized in Fig. 7, we see that dimensionality reduction as preprocessing performs worst across all drift detectors. Drift-informed

Fig. 5. Drift scores for selected drift detectors without feature selection (drift at 50%, sample size 250).

feature selection improves over considering all available features (all) in most cases.

Considering the used model type, we observe that the classifier-based (cls) approaches are outperformed by their regression-based counterparts (reg) for Boruta, MI, and PFI. For FI and RFE this depends on the used model. Here, the effect for RF is much stronger than for ET. Both approaches suffer the more the drift point is different from 50%, but classification base approaches usually suffer more. If we consider drift at 50% only, the classifier-based approaches increase in rank compared to the regression-based approaches and tend to outperform them. For example, in Boruta with RF reg is always better than cls if all rates are considered if we consider a rate of 50% only cls is always better than reg.

Concerning the sample size, we find that feature selection works better for the larger sample (250 datapoints) than for the smaller sample size (100 datapoints). Also, we observe that the different selection strategies are affected differently. We found no clear pattern.

We further investigate the obtained scores by focusing on the best-performing feature selection methods. In the following, we only consider one set of parameters (the best-performing ones as shown in Fig. 7) per feature selection algorithm. The overall ranking is shown in Fig. 8.

We observe significant differences between the different selection methods (Fisher test $p = 0.001$). This also holds true when results for

each drift detector are considered separately. In all cases, unsupervised dimensionality reduction performs worst. The proposed feature selection methods perform better than using all features, whereby the significance of improvement depends on the specific choices. Boruta (ET, reg) performs best.

Considering the mean ranks for every used drift detector we see that Boruta still performed best. In nearly all cases all is outperformed by all selection methods (except for KS and D3 with Logist Regression where PFI is outperformed by all) and the difference to the best is significant for all except KS.

For KS, all is in second place. However, considering Fig. 5 we see that KS suffers from the multi-testing problem, i.e., random noise is considered to be drift, while D3 with k -NN (and all other methods) shows problems extracting the relevant signal despite the noise. As can be seen, the latter becomes harder for dependent noise while that does not pose any problem for the feature-wise approach. Indeed, if we consider dependent and independent noise separately, all is in the first and third place, respectively, for KS.

From this experiment, we conclude that using feature selection as proposed in this paper can significantly increase the performance of drift detection. This effect is stronger for methods that give equal relevance to all features. Furthermore, we showed that commonly used methods to reduce the number of features like PCA or random projection tend to be harmful to the detection performance.

Fig. 6. Visualization of ROC-AUCs for selected drift detectors without feature selection on the Nebraska Weather dataset (drift at 50%, sample size 250).

7. Discussion

In this work, we studied the notion of concept drift on a feature-wise level. We modeled the notion of drifting features by considering a performance increase in drift detection algorithms. In particular, by studying the relationship between drifting features and concepts from feature relevance theory, we derived an algorithmic scheme that allows for several practical instantiations. The resulting algorithms can be considered in the more general algorithmic scheme of model-based drift explanations [8]. We then concluded by studying which parts of the drift detection algorithm may or may not have an impact on the resulting notion of drifting features on a theoretical level.

In the empirical evaluation, we showed that the notion of drifting features serves as a reasonable notion of feature selection for drift detectors in the sense that they allow for an increase in performance in nearly all cases. We also showed that common uninformed techniques can be easily outperformed by our method on all considered setups.

The theoretical analysis of the impact of different properties of drift detectors, in particular on the used metric, is currently limited. In particular, the important case of limited model complexity is so far not well understood. Although we showed that an analysis of particular instantiations is possible, a theoretical framework that allows for a systematic analysis is currently lacking and subject to future research.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Fabian Hinder: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Valerie Vaquet:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Barbara Hammer:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Code is publicly available, data are standard benchmarks.

Acknowledgments

Funding in the frame of the ERC Synergy Grant “Water-Futures” No. 951424 is gratefully acknowledged.

Fig. 7. Summary of experiment. Mean ranks over all experiments. Lowest stage is number of selected features.

Fig. 8. Visualization of ranking over all experiments showing results of post-hoc Nemenyi test (critic distance (CD) for $p = 0.005$). Brackets show model, model type (if available), and number of selected features/selection strategy.

Appendix. Proofs, additional statements, and examples

For the generalization of [Example 1](#), we adapt the ideas from [\[27\]](#):

Lemma 2. *Let \mathbf{F} be finite and $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ any subset. Assume $|\mathcal{X}_f| \geq 2$ for all $f \in \mathbf{F}$. Then there is a distribution process D_t on \mathcal{X} with drift such that $D_t(X_{F'})$ has no drift for any $F' \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ with $F \not\subseteq F'$.*

Proof. W.l.o.g. w.m.a. $F = \{f_1, \dots, f_n\}$.

First consider the case $F = \mathbf{F}$ and $\mathcal{T} = \mathcal{X}_f = \{-1, 1\}$. Let $\varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3, \dots, \varepsilon_n, \varepsilon_T$ be independent Rademacher distributed, i.e., $\mathbb{P}[\varepsilon_i = -1] = \mathbb{P}[\varepsilon_i = 1] = 1/2$. It is easy to see that $\varepsilon_1 = \varepsilon_2 \cdot \varepsilon_3 \cdot \dots \cdot \varepsilon_n \cdot \varepsilon_T$ is also Rademacher. We have to show that $\varepsilon_T \perp (\varepsilon_i)_{i \in F'}$ if and only if $F' \neq \mathbf{F}$. Consider:

$$\varepsilon_T \perp (\varepsilon_i)_{i \in F'} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\Leftrightarrow 0 = \sup_{A \subseteq \mathcal{T}, B \subseteq \mathcal{X}_{F'}} |\mathbb{P}[\varepsilon_T \in A, (\varepsilon_i)_{i \in F'} \in B] - \mathbb{P}[\varepsilon_T \in A] \mathbb{P}[(\varepsilon_i)_{i \in F'} \in B]| \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$= \sup_{A \subseteq \mathcal{T}, B \subseteq \mathcal{X}_{F'}} |\text{Cor}(\mathbb{I}_A(\varepsilon_T), \mathbb{I}_B((\varepsilon_i)_{i \in F'}))| \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\stackrel{!^1}{=} \sup_{p, q \text{ polynomial}} \text{Cor}(p(\varepsilon_T), q((\varepsilon_i)_{i \in F'})) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\stackrel{!^2}{=} \sup_{a \in \mathcal{P}(F')^{\mathbb{R}}} \sum_{F'' \subseteq F'} a_{F''} \text{Cor}\left(\varepsilon_T, \prod_{i \in F''} \varepsilon_i\right) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

$$\Leftrightarrow 0 = \sup_{F'' \subseteq F'} \text{Cor}\left(\varepsilon_T, \prod_{i \in F''} \varepsilon_i\right) \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$= \sup_{F'' \subseteq F'} \mathbb{E}\left[\varepsilon_T \cdot \left(\prod_{i \in F''} \varepsilon_i\right)\right] - \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_T]}_{=0} \cdot \mathbb{E}\left[\prod_{i \in F''} \varepsilon_i\right], \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where $!^1$ holds since $\{-1, 1\}^{n+1}$ is finite and we can thus represent every function as a polynomial, and $!^2$ by linearity of covariance and since $\varepsilon_i^k = \varepsilon_i$ if k is odd and $\varepsilon_i^k = 1$ if k is even. For $F' = \mathbf{F}$, by definition of ε_1 we have $\varepsilon_1 \cdot \varepsilon_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \varepsilon_n \cdot \varepsilon_T = \varepsilon_2^2 \cdot \dots \cdot \varepsilon_n^2 \cdot \varepsilon_T^2 = 1$ thus the expectation is 1, too. Otherwise, at least one ε_i does only occur once and so the resulting product is Rademacher and hence has expectation 0.

For all other cases, choose any distribution $P_{\mathbf{F} \setminus F}$ on $\mathcal{X}_{\mathbf{F} \setminus F}$ and for $\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{X}_f$ with $f \in F$ choose two distributions $P_T^{(i)}$ and $P_f^{(i)}$, $i \in \{-1, 1\}$ each and consider the distribution process associated with the holistic distribution

$$D = \frac{1}{2^{|\mathbf{F}|}} \sum_{i_T, i_2, \dots, i_n \in \{-1, 1\}} P_T^{(i_T)} \times P_{f_1}^{(i_T, i_2, i_3, \dots, i_n)} \times P_{f_2}^{(i_2)} \times \dots \times P_{f_n}^{(i_n)} \times P_{\mathbf{F} \setminus F}. \quad \square \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Proposition 1. *Let D_t be a distribution process and $F' \subseteq F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$. X_F has no conditional drift given $X_{F'}$ if and only if $D_t(X_F)$ factors as $D_T(X_F | X_{F'})D_t(X_{F'})$.*

Proof. As shown in [\[17\]](#) X_F has no real drift given $X_{F'}$ if and only if $X_F \perp T | X_{F'}$ which by definition is equal to

$$D_W[X_F \in A, X_{F'} \in B] \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$= \mathbb{P}[X_F \in A, X_{F'} \in B | T \in W] \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$= \mathbb{P}[X_F \in A | T \in W, X_{F'} \in B] \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in B | T \in W] \quad (\text{A.11})$$

$$= \mathbb{P}[X_F \in A | X_{F'} \in B] \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in B | T \in W] \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$\stackrel{!}{=} \mathbb{P}[X_F \in A | T \in \mathcal{T}, X_{F'} \in B] \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in B | T \in W] \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$= D_T[X_F \in A | X_{F'} \in B] D_W[X_{F'} \in B] \quad (\text{A.14})$$

for all $A \subseteq \mathcal{X}_F, B \subseteq \mathcal{X}_{F'}, W \subseteq \mathcal{T}$, with B and W non-null sets. Here $!$ holds because $\mathbb{P}[T \in \mathcal{T}] = 1$ and the first and last equality are just the definitions. Thus, the holistic distribution factors as $D(X_F, X_{F'}, T) =$

$D_T(X_F | X_{F'})D(X_{F'}, T)$ which in turn uniquely determines the kernel D_t via Fubini showing the statement. \square

Lemma 1. *Let D_t be a distribution process and $(X, T) \sim \mathcal{D}$ a sample point. The Kullback–Leibler drift intensity is monotonic with respect to set inclusion, i.e., for $F' \subseteq F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ we have*

$$0 = I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(\emptyset) \leq I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(F') \stackrel{(*)}{\leq} I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(F) \leq I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(\mathbf{F}). \quad (\text{A.15})$$

Equality holds in $(*)$ if and only if X_F has no conditional drift given $X_{F'}$. In particular, $I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(F) = 0$ if and only if $D_t(X_F)$ has no drift and $I_{D_t, \text{KL}}(\mathbf{F}) = 0$ if and only if D_t has no drift.

Proof. Using the connection of Kullback–Leibler divergence and mutual information we observe that the Kullback–Leibler drift intensity is just the mutual information of data and time:

$$I_{D_t, D_{\text{KL}}}(F) = \int D_{\text{KL}}(D_t(X_F) \parallel D_T(X_F)) dP_T(t) \quad (\text{A.16})$$

$$= \mathbb{E}_{T \sim P_T}[D_{\text{KL}}(\mathbb{P}_{X_F|T} \parallel \mathbb{P}_{X_F})] \quad (\text{A.17})$$

$$= I(T; X_F), \quad (\text{A.18})$$

where $T \sim P_T$ is a random variable representing time. Using the concept of conditional mutual information we can write $I_{D_t, D_{\text{KL}}}(F) = I_{D_t, D_{\text{KL}}}(F') + I(T; X_F \setminus F' | X_{F'})$. It is well known that $I(T; X_F \setminus F' | X_{F'}) \geq 0$ so we have monotonicity and equality holds if and only if T and $X_F \setminus F'$ are independent given $X_{F'}$ which is the case if and only if X_F has no conditional drift given $X_{F'}$ by [Proposition 1](#).

Lemma 3. *For a distribution process D_t denote by $R(D_t, F) = \{f | I_{D_t}(f) < I_{D_t}(F \cup \{f\})\}$ for any drift intensity I . Then we can write*

$$R(D_t) = \bigcup_{F \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{F})} R(D_t, F) \quad (\text{A.19})$$

Proof. We have $f \in R(D_t)$ if and only if there is a $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ such that $I_{D_t}(f) < I_{D_t}(F \cup \{f\})$ which holds if and only if $f \in R(D_t, F)$. \square

Proposition 5. *For any drift intensity I and distribution process D_t we have that $N(D_t)$ is the largest subset that leaves the drift intensity unchanged, i.e., if $N \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ such that $I_{D_t}(F) = I_{D_t}(F \cup N)$ for all $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ then $N \subseteq N(D_t)$.*

Furthermore, every feature that is drifting for a subset of features is also drifting for all features, i.e., if $F' \subseteq F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ then $R(D_t(X_{F'})) \subseteq R(D_t(X_F))$.

Proof. Assume there is a $N \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ such that $I_{D_t}(F) = I_{D_t}(F \cup N)$ for all F and N is not a subset of $N(D_t)$. Then, there exists a drifting feature $f \in N$ and hence a set $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ such that

$$I_{D_t}(F) < I_{D_t}(F \cup \{f\}) \leq I_{D_t}(F \cup N) \quad (\text{A.20})$$

where the second inequality is just monotonicity. This is a contradiction.

The second statement follows by [Lemma 3](#) using that $F' \subseteq F$ implies $\mathcal{P}(F') \subseteq \mathcal{P}(F)$. \square

Proposition 6. *Let D_t be a distribution process. For any drift intensity I that detects drift, i.e., if D_t has drift then $I_{D_t}(\mathbf{F}) > 0$, it holds that D_t has drift if and only if $R(D_t)$ is not empty. Conversely, $N(D_t)$ is a proper subset of \mathbf{F} if and only if D_t has drift.*

In particular, if D_t has drift then there exists at least one drifting feature.

Proof. Let $\mathbf{F} = \{f_1, \dots, f_n\}$ and denote by $u(k) = I_{D_t}(\{f_1, \dots, f_k\})$. Then by monotony, we have that

$$0 = u(0) \leq \dots \leq u(n) = I_{D_t}(\mathbf{F}) \quad (\text{A.21})$$

and $u(n) = 0$ if and only if \mathcal{D}_t has no drift by assumption. If $u(n) > 0$ then there must be a smallest i such that $u(i) > 0$ and therefore

$$I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(\{f_1, \dots, f_{i-1}\}) = u(i-1) < u(i) = I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(\{f_1, \dots, f_{i-1}, f_i\}) \quad (\text{A.22})$$

so f_i is a drifting feature. \square

Proposition 7. For the Kullback–Leibler drift intensity (or more generally any drift intensity induced by an f -divergence), let \mathcal{D}_t be a distribution process and A be a kernel on $\mathcal{X}_{N(\mathcal{D}_t)}$. Then $R(\mathcal{D}_t) = R(\Gamma_A \mathcal{D}_t)$ where $\Gamma_A \mathcal{D}_t$ appends the result of A as new features, i.e., $(\Gamma_A \mathcal{D}_t)(C \times B) = \int_B A(\text{proj}_{N(\mathcal{D}_t)}(x), C) d\mathcal{D}_t(x)$. In particular, the following do not introduce drift:

1. Adding a noise feature, i.e., $A(C | x) = \mathbb{P}[\varepsilon \in C]$ with ε independent noise
2. Processing non-drifting data, i.e., $A(C | x) = \delta_{f(x)}(C)$ for any measurable map f on $\mathcal{X}_{N(\mathcal{D}_t)}$
3. Any concatenation of the above

Proof. Denote by $N = N(\mathcal{D}_t)$ and by f' the new feature introduced by A . For all $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ we have

$$I_{\mathcal{D}_t, \text{KL}}(F) \stackrel{!1}{=} I_{\Gamma_A \mathcal{D}_t, \text{KL}}(F) \quad (\text{A.23})$$

$$\stackrel{!2}{\leq} I_{\Gamma_A \mathcal{D}_t, \text{KL}}(F \cup \{f'\}) \quad (\text{A.24})$$

$$\stackrel{!2}{\leq} I_{\Gamma_A \mathcal{D}_t, \text{KL}}(F \cup \{f'\} \cup N) \quad (\text{A.25})$$

$$\stackrel{!3}{\leq} I_{\mathcal{D}_t, \text{KL}}(F \cup N) \quad (\text{A.26})$$

$$\stackrel{!4}{=} I_{\mathcal{D}_t, \text{KL}}(F) \quad (\text{A.27})$$

where $!1$ holds because \mathcal{D}_t and $\Gamma_A \mathcal{D}_t$ coincide on \mathbf{F} , $!2$ is given by monotonicity, $!3$ holds because $D_{\text{KL}}(\kappa P \parallel \kappa Q) \leq D_{\text{KL}}(P \parallel Q)$ for any kernel κ so in particular for Γ_A , and $!4$ by Proposition 5. Thus, $I_{\Gamma_A \mathcal{D}_t, \text{KL}}(F) = I_{\Gamma_A \mathcal{D}_t, \text{KL}}(F \cup \{f'\})$ for any $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}$ and hence f' is non-drifting. \square

Proposition 8. For any drift intensity I let \mathcal{D}_t be a distribution process. We define the drift value of a feature $f \in \mathbf{F}$ as the Shapley value associated to I :

$$S_{\mathcal{D}_t}(f) := \frac{1}{|\mathbf{F}|} \sum_{F \subseteq \mathbf{F} \setminus \{f\}} \binom{|\mathbf{F}|-1}{|F|} (I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(F \cup \{f\}) - I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(F)). \quad (\text{A.28})$$

Then it holds $S_{\mathcal{D}_t}(f) \geq 0$ and equality holds if and only if f is not drifting.

Proof. Use that $I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(F \cup \{f\}) - I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(F) \geq 0$ by monotonicity and thus $S_{\mathcal{D}_t}(f) > 0$ implies that $I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(F' \cup \{f\}) - I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(F') > 0$ for some F' . \square

Example 3. Consider a distribution process with $\mathcal{T} = \{0, 1\}$, $P_T = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{T})$. Let I be a drift intensity such that $I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(F) \leq I_{\mathcal{D}_t, \text{TV}}(F)$ and if $\mathcal{D}_0(X_f) = \lambda \delta_{p_1} + (1 - \lambda) \delta_{p_2}$ and $\mathcal{D}_1(X_f) = (1 - \lambda) \delta_{p_1} + \lambda \delta_{p_2}$ for $\lambda \in [0, 1]$, $p_1, p_2 \in \mathcal{X}_f$ then $I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(\{f\}) = 4|1/2 - \lambda| = I_{\mathcal{D}_t, \text{TV}}(\{f\})$. Such drift intensities are not uncommon as they are for example induced by the accuracy of classifiers.

Assume that I only increases if the added features are conditionally drifting. Let \mathcal{D}_t be a distribution process such that f is a drifting feature with respect to total variation for F (and thus conditionally drifting given F) but $I(F) = I(F \cup \{f\})$ (see Example 4 for a concrete example). By the Hahn decomposition theorem, there exists a set A such that $I_{\mathcal{D}_t, \text{TV}}(F \cup \{f\}) = 2(\mathcal{D}_0[(X_F, X_f) \in A] - \mathcal{D}_1[(X_F, X_f) \in A])$. Introduce a new feature f' by setting $X_{f'} = p_0$ if $(X_F, X_f) \in A$ and $X_{f'} = p_1$ otherwise, so that $I_{\mathcal{D}_t, \text{TV}}(F \cup \{f\}) = I_{\mathcal{D}_t, \text{TV}}(\{f'\})$. We thus have

$$I_{\mathcal{D}_t, \text{TV}}(F) \geq I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(F) \quad (\text{A.29})$$

$$\stackrel{!1}{=} I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(F \cup \{f\}) \quad (\text{A.30})$$

$$\stackrel{!2}{=} I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(F \cup \{f, f'\}) \quad (\text{A.31})$$

$$\geq I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(\{f'\}) \quad (\text{A.32})$$

$$= I_{\mathcal{D}_t, \text{TV}}(\{f'\}) \quad (\text{A.33})$$

$$= I_{\mathcal{D}_t, \text{TV}}(F \cup \{f\}) \quad (\text{A.34})$$

$$\stackrel{!1}{>} I_{\mathcal{D}_t, \text{TV}}(F) \quad (\text{A.35})$$

where $!1$ holds by choice of f and $!2$ holds because $X_{f'}$ is a deterministic function of X_F, X_f and thus cannot have conditional drift. This is a contradiction!

Thus, IPM-induced drift intensities that separate points and not increases if and only if there is conditional drift either miss drifting features or increase in some cases even if there is no conditional drift.

Example 4. Consider the distribution process based on the following functional model: $\mathcal{T} = \{0, 1\}$, $P_T = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{T})$, $X_1 \sim \mathcal{U}(\{1, \dots, N\})$ independent of T , and $X_2 = X_1 + \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon T$ where $\varepsilon \sim \mathcal{U}(\{0, 1\})$ independent noise. As we can easily reconstruct T, X_1, ε from X_2 by rounding, we see that X_1 is also conditionally independent of T given X_2 and thus not a drifting feature (according to Kullback–Leibler and total variation). Yet, if we use $I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(F) = d_{\text{linear}}(\mathcal{D}_0(X_F), \mathcal{D}_1(X_F))$ the IPM based on linear classifiers then we have $I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(\{2\}) = \frac{1}{N}$ so the detection strength gets arbitrarily low as $N \rightarrow \infty$. On the other hand, since we can easily reconstruct T from X_1, X_2 using the linear model $T = \mathbb{1}[X_2 - X_1 > 1/2]$ we have $I_{\mathcal{D}_t}(\{1, 2\}) = 1$.

Hence, we can say that X_1 is conditionally drifting given X_2 in the context of drift detectors based on linear models because the inverse of the function that computes X_2 from T, X_1, ε exists but as it is not linear.

Theorem 2. Let \mathcal{D}_t be a distribution process with features \mathbf{F} . Let (X, T) be a sample point drawn from \mathcal{D}_t , i.e., $(X, T) \sim \mathcal{D}$ is a pair of random variables. A feature f is drifting (in the sense of Kullback–Leibler) if and only if X_f is relevant to T . The set of all drifting features is given by a solution to the all-relevant problem for T , i.e., $R_{\text{KL}}(\mathcal{D}_t) = R(T | X_{\mathbf{F}})$.

Proof. The first part is obvious by Lemma 1 as a feature is drifting if and only if there is a set of features F such that $T \not\perp X_f | X_F$. For the all-relevant part use Proposition 5. \square

Theorem 3. Let \mathcal{B}_0 be an intersection stable generator of the σ -algebra of \mathcal{T} . The following are equivalent:

1. $X_{F'}$ is conditional drifting given X_F .
2. There is a time window $W \in \mathcal{B}_0$ such that W, \mathcal{T} witness the conditional drift of $X_{F'}$ given X_F .
3. There is a time window $W \in \mathcal{B}_0$ such that W, W^C witness the conditional drift of $X_{F'}$ given X_F .
4. There are disjoint time windows W_1, W_2 with $W_1, W_2^C \in \mathcal{B}_0$ such that W_1, W_2 witness the conditional drift of $X_{F'}$ given X_F .
5. If \mathcal{B}_0 contains a countable cover of \mathcal{T} , i.e., $\exists B_i \in \mathcal{B}_0 : \bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} B_i = \mathcal{T}$, then there are time windows $W_1, W_2, W_3 \in \mathcal{B}_0$ such that W_1, W_2 and $W_1, W_3 \setminus W_1$ or $W_1 \setminus W_3, W_3$ witness the conditional drift of $X_{F'}$ given X_F .
6. There are time windows W_1, W_2 that witness the conditional drift of $X_{F'}$ given X_F .

In all cases above we always witness the same A (and B).

Proof. In addition to the above, we also show that in cases 2-6 we always witness the same drift, i.e., the same A and B . Here, for 1. we say that we witness A (given and B) if and only $\mathbb{1}[X_{F'} \in A]$ is (conditionally) drifting (given $\mathbb{1}[X_F \in B]$). Furthermore, W in 2 and 3 and W_1 in 4 and 5 refer to the same window, and if $W_1 \in \mathcal{B}_0$ in 6 then it also refers to the same window.

For the rest of the proof denote by

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{A,B,W_1}(W_2) &= \mathbb{P}[X_F \in A, X_{F'} \in B, T \in W_1] \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in B, T \in W_2] \\ &\quad - \mathbb{P}[X_F \in A, X_{F'} \in B, T \in W_2] \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in B, T \in W_1] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.36})$$

Notice that $\mu_{A,B,T}$ and $\mu_{A,B,W}$ are finite measures, $\mu_{A,B,W_1}(W_2) = -\mu_{A,B,W_2}(W_1)$, and $\mu_{A,B,W}(W) = 0$ for all $W, W_1, W_2 \subseteq \mathcal{T}$.

We refer to the following statement as “2’”): There is a time window W (not necessarily $W \in \mathcal{B}_0$) such that W, \mathcal{T} witness the conditional drift of $X_{F'}$ given X_F .

1) \Leftrightarrow 2’): there is conditional drift if and only if $X_F \not\perp T \mid X_{F'}$ by **Proposition 1** which holds if and only if there are A, B, W for which we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbb{P}[X_F \in A, X_{F'} \in B, T \in W] \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in B] \\ &\neq \mathbb{P}[X_F \in A, X_{F'} \in B] \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in B, T \in W]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.37})$$

Using that $\mathbb{P}[T \in \mathcal{T}] = 1$ we can add a respective term

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbb{P}[X_F \in A, X_{F'} \in B, T \in W] \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in B] \\ &= \mathbb{P}[X_F \in A, X_{F'} \in B, T \in W] \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in B, T \in \mathcal{T}] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.38})$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbb{P}[X_F \in A, X_{F'} \in B] \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in B, T \in W] \\ &= \mathbb{P}[X_F \in A, X_{F'} \in B, T \in \mathcal{T}] \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in B, T \in W]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.39})$$

Since $\mu_{A,B,T}(W)$ is the difference of the extended terms, independence holds if and only if $\mu_{A,B,T}(W) = 0$ if and only if W, \mathcal{T} do not witness the drift. Thus, the statement follows as we may choose any A, B, W .

2’) \Rightarrow 2): it holds $\mu_{A,B,T}(W) \neq 0$. Assume there is no $W' \in \mathcal{B}_0$ such that W', \mathcal{T} witness the drift at A given B . Then $\mu_{A,B,T}(W') = 0$ for all $W' \in \mathcal{B}_0$. Furthermore, it is clear that $\mu_{A,B,T}(\mathcal{T}) = 0$ and $|\mu_{A,B,W_1}| \leq 2$ is finite. As $\mu_{A,B,T}$ coincides with the 0-measure on \mathcal{T} and on an intersection-stable generator we have that $\mu_{A,B,T} = 0$ and thus $\mu_{A,B,T}(W) = 0$ which is a contradiction.

2) \Rightarrow 3): since $\mathcal{T} = W \sqcup W^C$ it holds

$$0 \neq -\mu_{A,B,T}(W) \quad (\text{A.40})$$

$$= \mu_{A,B,W}(\mathcal{T}) \quad (\text{A.41})$$

$$= \mu_{A,B,W}(W) + \mu_{A,B,W}(W^C) \quad (\text{A.42})$$

$$= \mu_{A,B,W}(W^C) \quad (\text{A.43})$$

3) \Rightarrow 4): take $W_1 = W, W_2 = W^C$

4) or 5) \Rightarrow 6): clear

6) \Rightarrow 2’): assume neither W_1, \mathcal{T} nor W_2, \mathcal{T} witness the conditional drift at A given B . Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in A, X_F \in B, T \in W_1] \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B] \\ &= \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in A, X_F \in B] \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B, T \in W_1]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.44})$$

On the other hand, since $\mathbb{P}[X_F \in B] \geq \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B, T \in W_1] > 0$ we have

$$0 \neq \mu_{A,B,W_1}(W_2) \quad (\text{A.45})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Leftrightarrow &\mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in A, X_F \in B, T \in W_1] \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B, T \in W_2] \\ &\neq \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in A, X_F \in B, T \in W_2] \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B, T \in W_1] \quad | \cdot \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.46})$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in A, X_F \in B] \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B, T \in W_1] \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B, T \in W_2] \quad (\text{A.47})$$

$$= \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in A, X_F \in B, T \in W_1] \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B] \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B, T \in W_2] \quad (\text{A.48})$$

$$\neq \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in A, X_F \in B, T \in W_2] \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B] \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B, T \in W_1] \quad (\text{A.49})$$

$$= \mathbb{P}[X_{F'} \in A, X_F \in B] \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B, T \in W_2] \mathbb{P}[X_F \in B, T \in W_1] \quad (\text{A.50})$$

which is a contradiction.

2) & \mathcal{B}_0 contains a countable cover of $\mathcal{T} \Rightarrow$ 5): assume $\mu_{A,B,W_1}(W_2) = 0$ for all $W_2 \in \mathcal{B}_0$. Since \mathcal{B}_0 contains a countable cover of \mathcal{T} and together with $|\mu_{A,B,W_1}| \leq 2$ is finite, this implies that μ_{A,B,W_1} is equal to the 0-measure. This is a contradiction as $\mu_{A,B,W_1}(\mathcal{T}) \neq 0$. The existence of W_3 is proven analogously using $\mathcal{B}'_0 = \{W' \setminus W_1 \mid W' \in \mathcal{B}_0\} \cup \{W_1 \cap W' \mid W' \in \mathcal{B}_0\}$ instead of \mathcal{B}_0 and apply the argument from “2) \Rightarrow 3)” if necessary. \square

$\mathcal{B}'_0 \cup \{W_1 \cap W' \mid W' \in \mathcal{B}_0\}$ instead of \mathcal{B}_0 and apply the argument from “2) \Rightarrow 3)” if necessary. \square

Example 5. Consider $\mathcal{T} = \{-2, -1, 1, 2\}$ with $P_T(\{-2\}) = P_T(\{2\}) = 1/3$, $P_T(\{-1\}) = P_T(\{1\}) = 1/6$ and $\mathcal{X} = \{(-1, 0), (1, 0), (0, -1), (0, 1)\} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$ with $D_{\pm 2} = \delta_{(\pm 1, 0)}, D_{\pm 1} = \delta_{(0, \pm 1)}$ (here \mathcal{T} and \mathcal{X} are equipped with the power σ -algebra) and $\mathcal{B}_0 = \{\emptyset, \{-2\}, \{-2, -1\}, \{-2, -1, 1\}\}$ which is an intersection stable generator of the σ -algebra on \mathcal{T} . Consider the IPM induced by the axis-aligned linear models, i.e., $F = \{\mathbf{1}[\text{proj}_f(x) > \theta] \mid f \in \mathbf{F}, \theta \in \mathbb{R}\}$.

As can be seen $d_F(D_{\{-1\}}, D_{\{1\}}) = 1$ is optimally separated by $f^*(x) = \mathbf{1}[\text{proj}_2(x) > 0]$. Indeed, projecting onto the first component does not allow us to distinguish the distributions. However, for $W = \{-2\}$ or $W = \{-2, -1, 1\}$ we have $D_W(X_2) = D_{W^C}(X_2)$ so f^* cannot separate the distributions. For $W = \{-2, -1\}$ f^* can separate the distributions but since $D_W = \frac{1}{3}(2\delta_{(-1,0)} + \delta_{(0,-1)})$ and $D_{W^C} = \frac{1}{3}(2\delta_{(1,0)} + \delta_{(0,1)})$ considering the projection onto the first component allows for a better separation than projecting onto the second. Thus, although a function is optimal for detecting a drift for a certain window this does not imply that there is a window in \mathcal{B}_0 that allows optimal detection using that function.

Example 6. It may happen that a drifting feature is not relevant for a specific window. Consider $\mathcal{T} = \{-1, 0, 1\}$, $P_T = \mathcal{U}(\mathcal{T})$ and there are two drifts one between -1 to 0 induced by $X_1 = \mathbf{1}[T = -1]$ and one between 0 to 1 induced by $X_2 = \mathbf{1}[T = 1]$ then both features are drifting features but for $W_1 = \{0\}$ and $W_2 = \{1\}$ only X_2 provides relevant information.

Proposition 2. Let D_f be a f -divergence, then $I_{D_f, D_f}(F) = \int D_f(D_f(X_F) \parallel D_{\mathcal{T}}(X_F)) dP_{\mathcal{T}}(t)$ is a drift intensity. Furthermore, the drifting features induced by this drift intensity are a subset of those induced by the Kullback–Leibler drift intensity.

Proof. f -divergences are monotonic, non-negative with $D_f(P \parallel P) = 0$, and $D_f(R_{Y|X} P_X \parallel R_{Y|X} Q_X) = D_f(P_X \parallel Q_X)$ so in particular $D_f(R_Y P_X \parallel R_Y Q_X) = D_f(P_X \parallel Q_X)$. The second statement follows by **Proposition 1**. \square

Proposition 3. Let F be a model type on \mathcal{X} of bounded functions. The F -induced drift intensity is a drift intensity, i.e., I_F fulfills **Definition 5**, if the following holds for all $F \subseteq \mathbf{F}, f \in \mathbf{F}$:

1. models in $F(F)$ can be approximated by models in $F(F \cup \{f\})$, i.e., for all $h_1 \in F(F)$, $\varepsilon > 0$, and probability measures P on $\mathcal{X}_{F \cup \{f\}}$, there exists a $h_2 \in F(F \cup \{f\})$ such that $\|h_1 \circ \text{proj}_F - h_2\|_{L^1(P)} < \varepsilon$, and
2. axis-aligned slices of models in $F(F \cup \{f\})$ can be approximated by models in $F(F)$, i.e., for all $h_2 \in F(F \cup \{f\})$, $x \in \mathcal{X}_f$, $\varepsilon > 0$, and probability measures P on \mathcal{X}_F , there exists a $h_1 \in F(F)$ such that $\|h_2(\cdot, x) - h_1\|_{L^2(P)} < \varepsilon$.

Proof. Non-negativity and monotonic for the case $F' = \emptyset$ are obvious. **Monotonicity:** (For non-empty F') Let $\emptyset \neq F' \subseteq F$. If $|F \setminus F'| = 1$ then we are in the situation of the statement by identifying F' (from the definition) with F from the statement. Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Choose $h_1 \in F(F)$ a $\varepsilon/3$ -witness of $d_F(D_{W_1}(X_F), D_{W_2}(X_F))$, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| d_F(D_{W_1}(X_F), D_{W_2}(X_F)) - |\mathbb{E}[h_1(X_F) \mid T \in W_1] - \mathbb{E}[h_1(X_F) \mid T \in W_2]| \right| \\ &< \varepsilon/3. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.51})$$

Approximate h_1 by $h_2 \in F(F \cup \{f\})$ for $P = 1/2(D_{W_1}(X_F, X_f) + D_{W_2}(X_F, X_f))$ up to $\|h_1 \circ \text{proj}_F - h_2\|_{L^1(P)} < \varepsilon/12$. As $h_1(X_F) = h_1 \circ \text{proj}_F(X_F, X_f)$ it follows by Jensen’s inequality and the definition of P that

$$|\mathbb{E}[h_1(X_F) - h_2(X_F, X_f) \mid T \in W_1]| \quad (\text{A.52})$$

$$\leq \mathbb{E}[|h_1 \circ \text{proj}_F(X_F, X_f) - h_2(X_F, X_f)| \mid T \in W_1] \quad (\text{A.53})$$

$$\leq 2\|h_1 \circ \text{proj}_F - h_2\|_{L^1(P)} \leq \frac{2\varepsilon}{12}. \quad (\text{A.54})$$

Thus, together with the triangle inequality we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & |d_F(\mathcal{D}_{W_1}(X_F), \mathcal{D}_{W_2}(X_F)) \\ & - \mathbb{E}[h_2(X_F, X_f) | T \in W_1] - \mathbb{E}[h_2(X_F, X_f) | T \in W_2] | \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.55})$$

$$\leq \left(\frac{1}{3} + \frac{4}{12}\right) \varepsilon < \varepsilon \quad (\text{A.56})$$

and hence $d_F(\mathcal{D}_{W_1}(X_F), \mathcal{D}_{W_2}(X_F)) \leq d_F(\mathcal{D}_{W_1}(X_F, X_f), \mathcal{D}_{W_2}(X_F, X_f))$ as we obtained h_2 as a sub-optimal choice.

If $|F \setminus F'| > 1$ let $F \setminus F' = \{f_1, \dots, f_n\}$ reduce to the previous case by observing that in $I(F') \leq I(F' \cup \{f_1\}) \leq \dots \leq I(F' \cup \{f_1, \dots, f_n\}) = I(F)$ we only ever add one feature.

Not wrongly drift detecting: Let $F' \subseteq F$ and assume $X_{F \setminus F'} \perp\!\!\!\perp T, X_{F'}$.

First notice that for every $x \in \mathcal{X}_{F \setminus F'}$, $\varepsilon > 0$, P , and $h_2 \in \mathcal{F}(F)$ there is a $h_1 \in \mathcal{F}(F')$ such that $\|h_2(\cdot, x) - h_1\|_{L^1(P)} < \varepsilon$ by repeatedly applying the second assumption.

For convenience, denote by $A = F \setminus F'$ the set of additional features. Now, let $\varepsilon > 0$ and choose h_2 that approximates $d_{F(F)}(\mathcal{D}_{W_1}(X_{F'}, X_A), \mathcal{D}_{W_2}(X_{F'}, X_A))$ up to $\varepsilon/4$. Because $X_A \perp\!\!\!\perp T, X_{F'}$ we have that

$$\mathbb{E}[h_2(X_{F'}, X_A) | T \in W_i] = \int \mathbb{E}[h_2(X_{F'}, x) | T \in W_i] d\mathbb{P}_{X_A}(x) \quad (\text{A.57})$$

and by Fubini's theorem, Jensen's inequality, and the fact that \mathbb{P}_{X_A} is a probability measure we thus have

$$|\mathbb{E}[h_2(X_{F'}, X_A) | T \in W_1] - \mathbb{E}[h_2(X_{F'}, X_A) | T \in W_2]| \quad (\text{A.58})$$

$$= \left| \int \mathbb{E}[h_2(X_{F'}, x) | T \in W_1] - \mathbb{E}[h_2(X_{F'}, x) | T \in W_2] d\mathbb{P}_{X_A}(x) \right| \quad (\text{A.59})$$

$$\leq \int |\mathbb{E}[h_2(X_{F'}, x) | T \in W_1] - \mathbb{E}[h_2(X_{F'}, x) | T \in W_2]| d\mathbb{P}_{X_A}(x) \quad (\text{A.60})$$

$$\leq \sup_{x \in \mathcal{X}_A} |\mathbb{E}[h_2(X_{F'}, x) | T \in W_1] - \mathbb{E}[h_2(X_{F'}, x) | T \in W_2]|. \quad (\text{A.61})$$

Find a point x_0 to approximate the supremum up to $\varepsilon/8$ and then approximate $h_2(\cdot, x_0)$ by $h_1 \in \mathcal{F}(F')$ up to $\varepsilon/16$ for $P = \frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{D}_{W_1}(X_{F'}) + \mathcal{D}_{W_2}(X_{F'}))$. Then h_1 approximates $d_{F(F)}(\mathcal{D}_{W_1}(X_{F'}, X_A), \mathcal{D}_{W_2}(X_{F'}, X_A))$ up to less than ε . Thus we have $d_{F(F)}(\mathcal{D}_{W_1}(X_{F'}, X_A), \mathcal{D}_{W_2}(X_{F'}, X_A)) \leq d_{F(F')}(\mathcal{D}_{W_1}(X_{F'}), \mathcal{D}_{W_2}(X_{F'}))$ as h_1 is a sub-optimal choice. Yet, by monotonicity we have equality. \square

Proposition 4. Let \mathcal{F} be a model type. If one of the following holds

1. \mathcal{F} consists of binary classifiers $f : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ and is universal w.r.t accuracy, i.e., for all $g : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$, $\varepsilon > 0$, and P there exists $f \in \mathcal{F}$ such that $\mathbb{P}_{X \sim P}[g(X) = f(X)] > 1 - \varepsilon$.
2. \mathcal{F} contains probabilistic binary classifier $f : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and is universal w.r.t cross-entropy, i.e., for all Lipschitz continuous compactly supported $g : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $\varepsilon > 0$, and P there exists f such that $\mathbb{E}_{X \sim P}[D_{\text{KL}}(g(X) \| f(X))] < \varepsilon$.
3. \mathcal{F} contains binary classifiers of the form $f(x) = \text{sign}(h(x))$, and the model-functions $h : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are universal w.r.t L^1 -approximation, i.e., for all compactly supported Lipschitz continuous $g : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow [-1, 1]$, $\varepsilon > 0$, and P there exists h such that $\|g - h\|_{L^1(P)} < \varepsilon$.

then a feature is drifting w.r.t F if and only if it is drifting w.r.t total variation. In particular, the F -induced drift intensity is a drift intensity (in the sense of Definition 5).

For the proof of Proposition 4 we need the following standard result:

Lemma 4. On a standard Borel space, the compactly supported Lipschitz continuous functions are a dense subset of $L^p(\mu)$ for all $1 \leq p < \infty$ and finite measures μ .

Proof of Proposition 4. Let $\varepsilon > 0$, $P = \frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{D}_{W_1}(X_F) + \mathcal{D}_{W_2}(X_F))$ and $x \sim P$. By Hahn's decomposition theorem there is a $g : \mathcal{X}_F \rightarrow \{-1, 1\}$ such that $I_{D_i, \text{TV}}(F) = |\mathbb{E}[g(X_F) | T \in W_1] - \mathbb{E}[g(X_F) | T \in W_2]|$. We now approximate g by \mathcal{F} .

(1) Now use g to label P and choose $f \in \mathcal{F}(F)$ such that $\mathbb{P}[f(x) \neq g(x)] \leq \varepsilon/16$. Then

$$|\mathbb{E}[f(x)] - \mathbb{E}[g(x)]| \leq \mathbb{E}[|f(x) - g(x)|] \quad (\text{A.62})$$

$$= 2\mathbb{P}[f(x) \neq g(x)] \quad (\text{A.63})$$

$$\leq \frac{1}{8}\varepsilon \quad (\text{A.64})$$

Thus, $|\mathbb{E}[g(X_F) | T \in W_1] - \mathbb{E}[g(X_F) | T \in W_2]| \leq 2/8 \varepsilon$ and therefore by using the triangle inequality, and that $\mathcal{F}(F) \subseteq \text{TV}(F)$ we have $|I_{D_i, \text{TV}}(F) - I_{D_i, \mathcal{F}}(F)| \leq 4/8 \varepsilon < \varepsilon$. Hence, $I_{D_i, \text{TV}}(F) = I_{D_i, \mathcal{F}}(F)$.

(2) Approximate g in $L^1(P)$ by a compactly supported, Lipschitz continuous g_1 up to $\varepsilon/16$ and g_1 by $f \in \mathcal{F}(F)$ in D_{KL} up to $1/512 \varepsilon^2$. Then, by Pinsker's inequality, we have

$$|\mathbb{E}[f(x)] - \mathbb{E}[g(x)]| \leq \|f - g\|_{L^1} \quad (\text{A.65})$$

$$\leq \|f - g_1\|_{L^1} + \|g_1 - g\|_{L^1} \quad (\text{A.66})$$

$$\leq \mathbb{E}[\sqrt{2D_{\text{KL}}(g_1(x) \| f(x))}] + \|g_1 - g\|_{L^1} \quad (\text{A.67})$$

$$\leq \sqrt{2\mathbb{E}[D_{\text{KL}}(g_1(x) \| f(x))]} + \|g_1 - g\|_{L^1} \quad (\text{A.68})$$

$$\leq \sqrt{2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{512} \varepsilon^2\right)} + \frac{1}{16} \varepsilon = \frac{1}{8} \varepsilon. \quad (\text{A.69})$$

Thus, $I_{D_i, \text{TV}}(F) = I_{D_i, \mathcal{F}}(F)$, as in the last case.

(3) Approximate g by a compactly supported, Lipschitz continuous function g_1 and g_1 by h with $\text{sign} \circ h \in \mathcal{F}(F)$ both up to $\varepsilon/16$.

As g and $\text{sign} \circ h$ take on values $\{-1, 0, 1\}$, we have that the difference $|g(x) - \text{sign} \circ h(x)|$ is at most 2. Furthermore, if the distance is not 0 then the difference between $g(x)$ and $h(x)$ is at least 1 because $g(x) \neq 0$. Thus using Markov's inequality we get

$$\mathbb{E}[|g(x) - \text{sign} \circ h(x)|] \leq 2\mathbb{P}[g(x) \neq \text{sign} \circ h(x)] \quad (\text{A.70})$$

$$= 2\mathbb{P}[|g(x) - \text{sign} \circ h(x)| \geq 1] \quad (\text{A.71})$$

$$= 2\mathbb{P}[|g(x) - h(x)| \geq 1] \quad (\text{A.72})$$

$$\leq 2\mathbb{E}[|g(x) - h(x)|] \quad (\text{A.73})$$

$$\leq 2(\mathbb{E}[|g(x) - g_1(x)|] + \mathbb{E}[|g_1(x) - h(x)|]) \quad (\text{A.74})$$

$$\leq 2\left(\frac{1}{16}\varepsilon + \frac{1}{16}\varepsilon\right) = \frac{1}{8}\varepsilon \quad (\text{A.75})$$

Thus, $I_{D_i, \text{TV}}(F) = I_{D_i, \mathcal{F}}(F)$ follows as in that last two cases. \square

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